

EFFECTIVE MANAGERIAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract:

Communication is the process of creating and sharing clear ideas. Effective communication depends not on the accuracy of the facts but on the richness of the ideas. In any organisation it is the lively happening. It makes the environment lively by making meaningful interactions. It minimises arguments and confusions. In business, effective communication is needed for the success of the organisation which in turn leads to the goal achievement. Managers are expected to have influentive communicative skills which will solve the problem, increase oneness feeling among the workers, create new opportunities for their ideas and lead to accomplishment of goals. The task of a manager is motivating, influencing, and persuading the workers for the company's goal to be attained. He has to be efficient in internal operational communication, external operational communication and personal communication. This article deals with various zones of effective communication needed for the managers.

Key Words: Effective Communication, Managers, Influentive, Achieving Goal, Meaningful Interaction & Healthy Environment.

Introduction:

Managers in any organisation are the head of the task force who are expected to be good in relearning, innovation and listening. When he converse with the taskforce, his conversation is to be clear and create shared meaning. It is the primary management tool, to plan and organise work. As Norm Fjeldheim, (CIO-Qualcomm) observes, Business communication is vital for anyone with technical skills without which his career will get stalled. He also says that being able to communicate, one becomes always valuable. That is why managerial communication and its impact is prioritized in business world.

How a Conversation is to be?:

A conversation is a dynamic talking and listening. The quality of conversation depends more on the quality of the listening than the quality of speaking. Good listeners are effective speakers. So, when the manager wants to be effective, he has to be an active listener to his workforce. By proper eye contact, body position, nodding head, the listener influences the speaker. As communication is so important in business, businesses need people with good communicative skills.

To Make Successful Conversation:

All conversations have a context. No conversation is successful in an information vacuum.

For Successful Conversation a Manager has to look into the Following:

- ✓ Paying proper attention
- ✓ Choosing ideal time
- ✓ Calm place which will not distract the listener
- ✓ Enough time to pass on the information

As the manager is the responsible person for many activities of the company, these things are to be treated as vital. Fayol saw management as a five point function of planning, organising, commanding, co ordination and controlling. The manager has to plan for the message to be conveyed, coordinate the points and have a control over his language and the emotions of his self and the listeners. Then only the desired impact will result. In today's scenario many organisations are MBOs (Management by Objectives). As Ordiorne observes MBO is a way of thinking about management.

Ends – Means Chain of organisational objectives.

In achieving the organisational goal the manager plays the role of a motivator, coordinator and a supporter. His communication has more impact in achieving that. While having a meaningful interaction via communication, giving feedback or sharing appraisal with the employees become mandatory.

While Giving Feedback / Appraisal:

Clark (1995:187) indicates that “there is no single universally accepted model of performance management that can be used”. It is a term originated in North America to describe the set of techniques used to assess and give feedback as performance.

It includes,

An effective manager links the performance objectives of his employees to those of the organisation. For this the steps taken are:

- ✓ Involving the employees in decision making.
- ✓ Linking the employee rewards to individual performance.

The objective oriented manager increases the productivity of the employees with his role modelling, positive approach and leadership qualities. When he gives feedback, his words are motivating, influentive, trying to link the feedback with needs analysis to develop individual productivity ratio. No way he should de motivate, criticize the work force. He has to be an icon for them in motivating.

Feedback, as used as a tool of appraisal mostly listened by the employee in a mixed emotional status. The manager has to be very careful in transforming the feedback in such a way that it will bring in useful outputs in the form of service. His feedback should be encouraging to the employee to render his best service and also to motivate him to update his skill and knowledge as per the need.

As conversation is the stock exchange where we trade ideas, effective communication becomes mandatory to all living organisations (which are growing organisations). For efficient conversational skills, the employees have to relearn how to talk with each other frequently and on a meaningful level, without which the organisation cannot survive as it is the network of conversations .When the manager is capable of making key points in his conversation, he is a person with one of the most important life skills. A skilful combination of verbal and nonverbal communication will help the manager to pass on the ideas, information to his employees (Silent Managers -1971). By integration, upgrading ideas, sharing, a manager can influence the workforce to be achievers.

Change Management – Communication for it:

There are many things that are related to an organisation’s functioning. Sometimes there is a need for functional swap, downsizing of workers or closure of one unit. Such instances are likely to provoke the workers against the management. It is the effective communication of the manager who creates an understanding platform for the workers and see that they are compensated in some way to manage the change. Change management becomes effective with the manager’s clear and comforting communication. His way of communication makes the workers understand the situation and cope up with change management. In any situation, it is the communication of the manager which aids and fosters the company’s growth having good rapport with the employees.

Problem Solving:

Problems arise when there is gap between where you are and where you have to be. The manager has to be clear with the choice of strategies and the message delivery methods. If he is careful, the problem can be solved very easily. When he meets the team in person and discuss, words used, voice, facial expressions, gestures used determine the effect of the message. Using positive language helps in achieving what is desired.

Conclusion:

In short, a Manager’s effective communication becomes the basic tool which aids goal achievement. When communication is clear, with End Means connection, it will become a targeted one which results in positive changes and finally in success. As a manager’s job is complex and multidimensional, to perform his task effectively the manager needs effective communicative skill. The managers today face two buzz words- Change and Challenge. “Effective manager ship is putting first things first. Effective management is carrying it

out.” Stephen Covey. As observed by Covey, an effective manager processes information and delivers it in the right time in an effective way. Communication becomes a vital and influensive source of the manager who wants to be an achiever.

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